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1. Overview

Data used for Figure 1 originate from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) database (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search?result=sequence&limit=0&format=tsv&download=true>) downloaded on the 27th of April 2024 and represent metadata from 299,704,900 ENA accessions.

The categorization of individual sequences into the six categories (right side of Figure 1) was based upon a variety of metadata properties and legal understanding. For two of the UN groups (WHO CA+/PIP and ITPGRFA), categorization was based on the taxonomic identity of the Genetic Resource (GR) from which the nucleotide sequence, or Digital Sequence Information (DSI), originated. For the BBNJ treaty, the geographic origin (specifically international waters without additional country information) associated with the individual entry was used to place sequences in the BBNJ category (Figure 1, right-hand side). Sequences originating from humans, model organisms, and synthetic/chimeric sequences were grouped into the "Out-of-scope" category based upon current legal understanding of material scope (see point 2.3 for more details). Accessions associated with patents, regardless of their taxonomic affiliation or geographic origin, were grouped in the Patent category based upon the presence of the /PAT tag (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/patentdata/nucleotides>). These sequences are not necessarily the object of the claim of intellectual property *per se*, but are often reference material submitted as part of a patent application to ensure reproducibility of the patented invention. All remaining sequences were categorized under CBD as this Treaty has an otherwise all-encompassing geographical scope. However, temporal scope was not considered.

2. Detailed analysis of the assignment to various UN frameworks associated with each DSI accession

2.1. ITPGRFA

In order to classify the accessions associated with the ITPGRFA (Figure 1, right side), Annex I of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA) was used. Annex I includes a list of crop and forage plants that are covered by its multilateral system. The WiLDSI project mapped the organisms from Annex I to the NCBI taxonomy (<https://github.com/wildsi/wildsi/tree/main/data/annex>). The annotation was done manually by Andrew Hufton during the WiLDSI project (<https://wildsi.ipk-gatersleben.de/apex/wildsi/r/wildsi/home>), including assignment of subtaxa and manual curation of

36 each exception present in Annex I. In this study, we used the list created by the WiLDSI project in
37 December 2021 "as is." For ITPGRFA accessions, we also observed that although 84% of ENA
38 accessions have no **/country** metadata tags and thus cannot be associated with countries of origin in
39 our analysis, it is possible to trace the country of origin by consulting the original publication where
40 the accession was originally published. To note, the tag **/country** will be replaced by the tag
41 **/geographical_origin** from June 2024 ([https://ncbiinsights.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2023/12/14/update-
42 genbank-qualifier/](https://ncbiinsights.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2023/12/14/update-genbank-qualifier/)).

43

44 **2.2. WHO CA+/PIP**

45 To identify the accessions associated with the "WHO CA+/PIP" group (Figure 1, right side), the
46 information available in Annex 2 ([https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/annex-2-of-the-
47 international-health-regulations-\(2005\)](https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/annex-2-of-the-international-health-regulations-(2005))) of the International Health Regulations (2005) ([IHR](#)), and
48 from the WHO R&D ([https://www.who.int/observatories/global-observatory-on-health-research-
49 and-development/analyses-and-syntheses/who-r-d-blueprint/who-r-d-roadmaps](https://www.who.int/observatories/global-observatory-on-health-research-and-development/analyses-and-syntheses/who-r-d-blueprint/who-r-d-roadmaps)) and WHO PIP
50 (https://apps.who.int/gb/pip/pdf_files/pandemic-influenza-preparedness-en.pdf) plans were used.

51 **2.2.1 IHR**

52 IHR defines countries rights and obligations in handling public health events that have the potential
53 to cross borders. Under the IHR, States Parties are required to carry out an assessment of public
54 health events occurring within their territories utilizing the decision instrument (algorithm) provided
55 in Annex 2 of the Regulations (*Decision instrument for the assessment and notification of events
56 that may constitute a public health emergency of international concern*). The annex identifies three
57 possible events involving different diseases, the pathogens listed in each of the three events were
58 used to identify taxonomic units from which to map the tax_id to be associated with the group
59 "WHO CA+/PIP":

60 1. A case of the following diseases is unusual or unexpected and may have serious public health
61 impact, and thus shall be notified

- 62 • Smallpox
- 63 • Poliomyelitis due to wild-type poliovirus
- 64 • Human influenza caused by a new subtype
- 65 • Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS)

66

67 2. Any event of potential international public health concern, including those of unknown causes or
68 sources and those involving other events or diseases than those listed in the box on the left and the
69 box on the right shall lead to utilization of the algorithm

- 70 • "Disease X" (placeholder for an unidentified or hypothetical disease).

71

72 NOTE: This cannot be defined taxonomically and so was not included in the analysis.

73

74 3. An event involving the following diseases shall always lead to utilization of the algorithm,
75 because they have demonstrated the ability to cause serious public health impact and to spread
76 rapidly internationally

- 77 • Cholera
- 78 • Pneumonic plague
- 79 • Yellow fever
- 80 • Viral haemorrhagic fevers (Ebola, Lassa, Marburg)
- 81 • West Nile fever
- 82 • Other diseases that are of special national or regional concern, eg. dengue, Rift Valley fever,
83 and meningococcal disease.

84

85 2.2.2 WHO PIP

86 With regard to influenza-related taxonomic units, we focused our analysis on the units attributable
87 to influenza type A, since only influenza type A viruses are known to have caused pandemics.

88

89 2.2.3 WHO R&D

90 The remaining human pathogens for taxonomic categorization within the WHO CA+/PIP category
91 were collected from the global WHO R&D strategy (<https://www.who.int/observatories/global-observatory-on-health-research-and-development/analyses-and-syntheses/who-r-d-blueprint/background>), a list of diseases that require priority attention because they have epidemic
93 potential. The list consists of the following diseases:

94

- 95 • COVID-19
- 96 • Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever
- 97 • Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease
- 98 • Lassa fever
- 99 • Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) and severe acute respiratory
100 syndrome (SARS)
- 101 • Nipah and henipaviral diseases
- 102 • Rift Valley fever
- 103 • Zika
- 104 • Monkeypox
- 105 • "Disease X"

106

107 The following methodology was used to map individual pathogen to the corresponding tax_id:

108

109 a. **Identify Virus Names associated with each disease.** This information was collected from
110 Wikidata (<https://www.wikidata.org/>). For example, for Lassa fever, one of the most common virus
111 name used is "Lassa virus." <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q706845>.

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b. Confirmation and verification of the correspondence between if virus name and taxonomic name (including old taxonomic names). Once the vernacular name of the disease was obtained, the taxonomic name was sourced from Wikidata and ICTV taxonomy (<https://ictv.global/taxonomy>).

For example, "Lassa virus" was updated to "*Mammarenavirus lassaense*" in 2022:
https://ictv.global/taxonomy/taxondetails?taxnode_id=20131157&taxon_name=Lassa%20virus.

c. Identification of NCBI tax_id for each viral entity. Next, the scientific names from the ICTV taxonomy were used for a text search in the NCBI taxonomy Browser (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>) to retrieve the corresponding tax_id. In case of an updated scientific name, the updated entry from the ICTV taxonomy database and any obsolete entry from the NCBI taxonomy Browser were mapped the corresponding tax_id. This allowed retrieval of any ENA accession that may be associated to obsoleted taxonomic description.

d. Fetching of sub-tax_id

All sub-tax_id hierarchically associated to higher level pathogen tax_id were retrieved with TaxonKit (Shen et al. 2021) using the higher taxonomic units as queries.

e. Assignments of pathogen-associated ENA accessions to the WHO CA+/PIP group

All tax_id collected in steps c and d, were assembled in a list and the list was used to categorize all entries in the ENA database associated to the "WHO CA+/PIP" group (Figure 1, right side).

2.3. Out-of-scope category

All synthetic or chimeric sequences not under the scope of any of the four UN fora, or associated to a patent, were considered "out-of-scope" (Figure 1 right side). Additionally, all organisms listed as model organisms from the NCBI website (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser/wwwtax.cgi>), except *Oryza sativa* and *Zea mays* (included in the ITPGRFA group) and *Homo sapiens* (isolated as its own group), were categorized into the "out-of-scope" group (Figure 1 right side):

1. *Arabidopsis thaliana*
2. *Escherichia coli*
3. *Pneumocystis carinii*
4. *Bos taurus*
5. Hepatitis C virus
6. *Rattus norvegicus*
7. *Caenorhabditis elegans*

- 149 8. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*
- 150 9. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*
- 151 10. *Mus musculus*
- 152 11. *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*
- 153 12. *Danio rerio* (zebrafish)
- 154 13. *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*
- 155 14. *Takifugu rubripes*
- 156 15. *Dictyostelium discoideum*
- 157 16. *Xenopus laevis*
- 158 17. *Drosophila melanogaster*
- 159 18. *Plasmodium falciparum*
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161 **2.4. Patents category**

162 All sequences that had the dataclass category mapped with the string PAT were associated with the
163 category "Patents" (Figure 1, right-hand side).

165 **2.5 BBNJ assignment based on geographic information**

166 Assignment of accessions to the BBNJ group (Figure 1 right hand side), was done from the
167 information contained in the metadata field country and location, according to the following
168 principles:

170 - **Identification of a recognized ocean name with no reference to a country name:** In case the
171 country metadata field mention only the string one of the ocean names without reference to a
172 country, the accession is categorized in the BBNJ group., e.g. "Atlantic Ocean:Mid-Atlantic Ridge".
173 A full, curated list of recognized ocean names is available at
174 <https://github.com/wildsi/wildsi/tree/main/data/country>.

176 - **Identification of 'Ocean', 'sea' or 'bay' with reference to the name of a country :** In case the
177 location metadata field mention the term "ocean" "sea" or "bay" and an explicit reference to the
178 name of a country name in the country metadata field, the accession is considered to be "associated
179 with a country of origin" and therefore not assigned to the BBNJ group.e.g. "USA:Hawaii, Oahu
180 Island, Kaniaohe Bay". This is a less rigorous filter that enriches DSI data from coastal marine
181 environments.

183 Following this methodology, we attempted to assign ENA accessions to the BBNJ treaty, aware that
184 the data we extracted are an overestimate of the accessions that could potentially be associated with
185 the BBNJ group relying solely on well curate maritime information from the country:location
186 metadata fields of the ENA database. In addition, precedence was given to the information
187 contained in the country:location metadata fields over the tax_id with regard to assignment to the

188 BBNJ group which may lead to inconsistencies in annotations, such as in the following spurious
189 examples:

- 190 • ENA accessions with country:location metadata with information as such Mediterranean
191 sea, North sea, Japan Pacific Ocean, Mediterranean sea: Croatia, Baltic sea were assigned to
192 the BBNJ group, but it isn't certain that the ENA accessions were obtained from areas
193 beyond national jurisdiction rather than continental waters.
- 194 • Accessions from the Mediterranean area that according to taxonomy refer to the ITPGRFA,
195 but having the country:location metadata as Mediterranean_sea, are grouped in the BBNJ
196 group, e.g., accession KY673694.1 of *Medicago truncatula*

197
198 For any other accessions that were not assigned to the BBNJ following the procedure described
199 above, if the country field contained a text string, they were categorized as "DSI with associated
200 country of origin," otherwise they were categorized as "DSI without associated country of origin"
201 (green and red lines in Figure 1, respectively) and assigned to BBNJ.

202 203 **2.6. CBD category**

204 Accessions that did not fall into any of the other five categories, ITPGRFA, WHO CA+/PIP, BBNJ,
205 Out-of-scope and Patents, were mapped to the CBD, (Figure 1, right-hand side).

206 207 **3. Retrieval of the nucleotide sequences and the metadata associated with each entry**

208 Each unique Accession id (Unique sequence id) was downloaded as tab-separated values (.tsv)
209 using the ENA API (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/>) together with the following associate
210 metadata:

- 211 • country = "locality of isolation of the sequenced sample indicated in terms of political
212 names for nations, oceans or seas, followed by regions and localities", e.g.
213 country="Canada:Vancouver". For this analysis, country will be split into two fields,
214 country and location.
- 215 • dataclass = "Sub-dataset of the Nucleotide sequences dataset. e.g. PAT = Patents"
- 216 • scientific_name = "lowest taxonomic unit associated to the GR from which the nucleotide
217 sequence originates"
- 218 • tax_division = "Broader artificial taxonomic division, e.g. FNG = fungi"
- 219 • tax_id = "Unique taxonomic ID"

220 221 **4. Data analysis tools used**

222 The data was analyzed using the open-source computing framework Apache Spark (Zaharia et al.,
223 2016) and its Python API PySpark (Apache Spark version 3.4.1) and TaxonKit (Shen et al.
224 2021)The Sankey diagram was generated with SankeyMATIC (<https://sankeymatic.com/>) and
225 edited with BioRender (<https://www.biorender.com/>).

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228 **5. Taxonomic identification of nucleotide sequences**

229 Taxonomic analysis followed taxonomic standardization implemented by NCBI and adopted by the
230 International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC); the foundational initiative that
231 operates between DDBJ, EMBL-EBI and NCBI (Federhen, 2012; Sakamoto & Ortega, 2021). ENA
232 requires every entry in the database to possess a univocal taxonomic ID under the tax_id category
233 that define the exact taxonomical unit (mostly genus and species) associated to the GR from which
234 the entry originates. For example, each DSI accession belonging to rice (*Oryza sativa*) in the ENA
235 database is associated to a unique numerical identifier that characterizes the genus and species of
236 the genetic resource of origin (e.g. for *Oryza sativa*, tax_id = 4530). Tax_id allows therefore for the
237 precise taxonomic categorization of each nucleotide sequence. However, many of the organisms
238 included in Annex I of the ITPGRFA or the WHO CA+/PIP are not univocally identified at the
239 species level, but rather at the genus or family level.

240 The hierarchical categorization of taxonomies from NCBI allowed for the retrieval and
241 identification of taxonomic subunits cascading down from the higher levels to the lowest, to
242 accurately capture the affiliation of each nucleotide sequence to each of the treaties and
243 conventions, taking advantage of the NCBI taxonomic database, downloaded from NCBI's FTP
244 servers (<https://ftp.ncbi.nih.gov/pub/taxonomy/>).

245 For example, in order to curate the list of species associated with Annex I of the ITPGRFA, dump
246 files nodes.dmp and names.dmp containing the taxonomic information were used to complete the
247 taxonomic tree below each taxon using python customized methods. For example, for *Oryza sativa*
248 it's was possible to obtain its "*children*" taxa as follows:

- 249 • *Oryza sativa* (tax_id)
- 250 • *Oryza sativa Indica Group* (tax_id)
- 251 • *Oryza sativa aus subgroup* (tax_id)
- 252 • *Oryza sativa indica subgroup* (tax_id)

253

254 The taxonomic groupings on the left side of Figure 1 were created using TaxonKit (Shen et al.
255 2021) using the higher taxonomic units described by Schoch et al 2021 and available in the NCBI
256 Taxonomy browser (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser/wwwtax.cgi>)

257 Starting with the high-level taxonomic units like Archaea, Bacteria, etc., all respective lower
258 taxonomic units (i.e. kingdom, clade, phylum, family, etc.) were extracted by creating the
259 appropriate taxon_id lists.

260 The following 10 top-level taxonomic units were used to retrieve the lower taxonomic units, in
261 parentheses the names used on the left side of Figure 1 if different from the denomination of the
262 respective tax_id identifier (Taxonomy ID):

- 263 • Archaea, Taxonomy ID: 2157
- 264 • Bacteria, Taxonomy ID: 2
- 265 • Viruses [not monophyletic] (Moreira et al. 2009), Taxonomy ID: 10239
- 266 • Other sequences (Others), Taxonomy ID: 28384
- 267 • Unclassified sequences (Unclassified), Taxonomy ID: 12908
- 268 • *Homo sapiens* (Human), Taxonomy ID: 9606
- 269 • Viridiplantae (Green plants), Taxonomy ID: 33090
- 270 • Fungi, Taxonomy ID: 4751
- 271 • Metazoa without *Homo sapiens* (*Non-human animals*), Taxonomy ID: 33208 without 9606
272 (*Homo sapiens*)
- 273 • Other eukaryote [not monophyletic], Taxonomy ID: 2759 without 9606 (*Homo sapiens*),
274 without 33090 (Viridiplantae), without 4751 (Fungi), and without 33208 (Metazoa)

275
276 The 10 tax_id lists were used to categorize each ENA accession to the appropriate taxonomic
277 category.

- 278 • For 1.958.758 accessions (0.66% of the total), a taxonomic grouping could not be
279 determined (e.g., because the tax_id field was empty, or the tax_id was obsolete) and thus
280 these accessions have been included in the “Unclassified” group of Figure 1.

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Preprint Draft